

D 7.10

Report on Liaison Activities and International Cooperation

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building
trust and sustainability for CCAM

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
UC	Use Case
R&D	Research & Development
CCAM	Connected Cooperative Automated Mobility
PDI	Physical and Digital Infrastructure
WP	Work Package
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
TRA	Transport Research Arena
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
CAV	Connected and Automated Vehicles
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
AI	Artificial Intelligent
TPM	Trust Platform Module
LiDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer

1. Introduction

1.1. Project intro

PoDIUM aims to support advanced Use Cases (UC) of connected and cooperative automated mobility in real traffic conditions. Building on the proposed urban and highway UCs in the facilities of 3 well-equipped Living Labs in Germany, Italy and Spain, PoDIUM will tackle all the different requirements for availability and performance of connectivity as well as the different cooperation enablers per UC. The proposed UCs aim to advance a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital parts of the infrastructure.

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

The purpose of this Deliverable is to provide a structured and detailed account of the liaison activities and international cooperation initiatives conducted under Task 7.3 within Work Package 7 (WP7) of the PoDIUM project. WP7 encompasses the project's dissemination, exploitation, and international cooperation efforts, aimed at maximizing the visibility, impact, and adoption of PoDIUM's research in Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM). Task 7.3 supports these goals by establishing connections with relevant past and present EU and international research and development (R&D) initiatives, policy makers, and established networks. Through these activities, PoDIUM seeks to foster synergies, support knowledge transfer, and address barriers to deployment, contributing to the advancement and broader adoption of CCAM and 5G solutions across Europe.

This report describes PoDIUM's approach to liaison and cooperation, including the strategies and processes developed to guide Task 7.3 activities. These include the establishment of guidelines and documentation practices to ensure that all interactions with external partners are systematically planned, implemented, and tracked. PoDIUM has engaged with various R&D projects, while also building sustained partnerships with projects funded under the same EU call, such as Augmented CCAM.

An essential part of this Deliverable is the evaluation of Task 7.3 activities against two Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that reflect PoDIUM's outreach and collaboration goals. KPI-62 targets engagements with at least ten EU and international R&D initiatives, policy makers, and related organizations, supporting broad-reaching relationships that integrate PoDIUM's findings into wider CCAM-related advancements. KPI-63 focuses on collaboration with at least five C-ROADS initiatives across Europe, ensuring alignment with established Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) and contributing to their harmonization. Activities conducted under these KPIs include liaisons with European projects and policy bodies and participation in events such as workshops and the joint session at conferences, supporting the exchange of knowledge across the CCAM and 5G landscape.

Table 1 lists the R&D initiatives, policymakers and related organisations with which liaison activities have been conducted, categorised by KPI. This provides a summary of the engagements and cooperation efforts that support PoDIUM's goals.

Table 1: List of conducted liaison activities per KPI

KPI-62: Liaise with at least 10 EU and international R&D initiatives, policy makers and related organisations and network	KPI-63: Liaise with at least 5 C-ROADS actions across EU
1. AI-SEE	1. C-Roads TF2 Service Harmonisation
2. AITHENA	2. C-Roads Spain
3. Augmented CCAM	3. SCALE (Spain)
4. AWARD	4. SCALE (Italy)
5. CCAM Partnership	5. C-Roads Italy
6. CONDUCTOR	
7. CONNECT	
8. ConnRAD	
9. Cultural Road	
10. DS4MOVEUS	
11. ENVELOPE	
12. ESERCOM-D	
13. EVENTS	
14. FAME	
15. FRODDO	
16. GAMMS	
17. iEXODDUS	
18. IN2CCAM	
19. IN-MOVE by Railgroup	
20. Joint activity at Smart City Expo World Congress	
21. MODI	
22. ROADVIEW	
23. SHOW	
24. TANGENT	

In summarizing these activities, this report also offers guidance on the various liaison activities PoDIUM has undertaken. Full details of these activities are available in the following chapter with individual reports. By consolidating these activities, the deliverable not only meets reporting requirements, but also provides a reference for PoDIUM’s ongoing and future liaison efforts. The liaison activities are an important element for PoDIUM’s sustained contributions to CCAM and 5G advancements, further supporting dissemination and collaboration within the European R&D community.

1.3. Approach

Task 7.3 started in Month 7 of the project and was carried out in two structured phases: an initial planning and preparation phase, followed by the implementation and monitoring of liaison activities.

In Phase 1, the Liaison and Cooperation Guidelines were created. These guidelines define what qualifies as a liaison activity and clarify the distinction between liaison and dissemination activities. According to the guidelines, the following formats are considered liaison activities:

- Events such as workshops, sessions, technical meetings, and webinars on liaison topics with liaison contacts.
- Participation in events or workshops organized by liaison contacts to represent PoDIUM.
- Joint development of outputs such as papers or white papers with liaison contacts.
- Collaboration on presentations, such as invited sessions with liaison contacts.
- Review of deliverables or documents, either by a liaison contact for PoDIUM or vice versa, on a defined topic.

A liaison contact is an organisation, R&D project, network or association related to a technical or other community, with which the PoDIUM partners conduct liaison and cooperation activities within the PoDIUM Task 7.3.

A liaison/cooperation is established when activities following one of the liaison formats have been carried out.

These definitions are important because they determine whether an activity contributes to the required KPIs, thereby ensuring transparency when assessing whether a given activity meets the criteria.

Phase 1: Planning and Preparation (April - May 2023):

During the planning and preparation phase, guidelines and templates for conducting and documenting liaison and cooperation activities were developed. These materials were presented to project partners for review and discussion, enabling alignment on the approach and objectives. Additionally, an initial identification of potential topics for liaison and cooperation was established, along with the relevant contact persons and responsible partners. This was done to lay the basis for targeted engagements.

Phase 2: Implementation and Monitoring (from June 2023):

The second phase involved carrying out and monitoring the planned liaison and cooperation activities. Regular meetings were held to assess ongoing activities, track progress, and identify potential new

opportunities for collaboration. These interactions were documented and the outcomes and insights are summarised in this deliverable.

1.4. Standardization activities

Liaison activities also encompass standardisation activities. However, as these are a key part of Task 6.3, this deliverable only provides a brief description of the activities with the ETSI Technical Committees ITS and INT. A detailed description can be found in Deliverable D6.4.

1.4.1. ETSI Technical Committee ITS

Date/timeline of activity: January 2025

Format of activity: Technical contribution to standards and technical meetings

Topic(s) of activity: Specification of coding format for C-ITS messages

Description of activity: The Liaison with ETSI was setup to propose a change in the ETSI Technical Specification TS 102 894 for updating the confidence level (or accuracy level) of the yaw angle and speed of vehicle. The current values of confidence level are low, leading to dismiss lot of valuable measurements.

During the January ITS Technical Committee meeting, a contribution from FSCOM, on behalf of the PoDIUM project proposed to update the 2 confidence level values.

Results/outcomes/achievements: The ETSI ITS technical committee acknowledged the problem and planned to revise the specification of the specific Cooperative Perception Service messages instead of changing the base message format coding, which could raise backward compatibility issues.

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: UULM, BOSCH

Other relevant information: See D6.4 deliverable about Standardisation activities for more details.

1.4.2. ETSI Technical Committee INT

Date/timeline of activity: to be finalised March 2026

Format of activity: Technical contribution to standards and technical meetings

Topic(s) of activity: Technical report on about 5G based ITS application validation

Description of activity: The Liaison with ETSI was setup to include in the Technical Report TR 104 074, dealing with “Methodologies for Testing & Validation of Network Application based services over 5G networks”, results of PoDIUM use cases and related validation activities.

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- The ETSI INT technical committee approved the inclusion of PoDIUM Innovation Action in the Technical report TR 104 074. A new work item was created to report about PoDIUM use cases, evaluation KPIs and methodology results.
- The description of PoDIUM was included in the technical report annex, and the use case and validation results will be included during Q1 2026.

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: FSCOM

2. Description of Liaison Activities

This section provides details of the liaison activities conducted within the PoDIUM project. For each activity, the format, topic and outcomes are described. The activities are listed in chronological order.

2.1. AUGMENTED CCAM

Date/timeline of activity: Starting 25.10.2022

Format of activity: Collaboration meetings, Joint dissemination activities

Topic(s) of activity: Collaboration opportunities between projects, use case comparison, joint dissemination activities, final events/demos

Description of activity: Regular meetings established and focused on identifying synergies between PoDIUM and AUGMENTED CCAM, particularly in the areas of architecture development, use case comparison, and joint dissemination.

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Agreement that a joint paper/publication is feasible; ICCS to explore the possibility with partners (especially those involved in architecture development).
- Decision to identify similar use cases between the projects and compare outcomes to inform next steps.
- Discussion on producing a common dissemination video/webinar before project completion to highlight shared results, given both projects share the same Project Officer and research domains.
- Agreement that each project should invite the other to its final events and demonstrations.

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: ICCS

Other relevant information: Some of the joint activities included:

- ACCAM Pan-European Workshop (13/09/2023)
<https://podium-project.eu/event/accam-pan-european-workshop-no-regret-investments-of-physical-and-digital-communication-infrastructure-for-ccam/>
- RTR 2024 (06/02/2024) Parallel Session with ACCAM - 8A. CCAM and connectivity
<https://podium-project.eu/podium-at-the-rtr-conference-2024/>
- TRA2024 (17 April 2024) Special Session 4.4 “CCAM session on physical / digital Infrastructure”
<https://podium-project.eu/podium-explores-multi-connectivity-at-the-transport-research-arena-2024/>
- IEEE CAMAD (21 – 23 October 2024) Session 2: PDI (Physical and Digital Infrastructure) and communication developments as CCAM (Connected and Cooperative Automated Mobility) enablers
<https://camad2024.ieee-camad.org/pdi-physical-and-digital-infrastructure-and-communication-developments-ccam-connected-and>
- EUCAD2025 (joint booth)
<https://podium-project.eu/podium-demonstrates-innovative-ccam-solutions-at-eucad-2025/>

- ITSEU2025 – Joint session: Traffic efficiency and safety through CCAM: Enhancing PDI for VRUs and emergency response
<https://podium-project.eu/podium-at-the-its-european-congress-2025-advancing-ccam-technologies/>

2.2. SHOW

Date/timeline of activity: 27.10.2022

Format of activity: One-day workshop on future technologies in Turin

Topic(s) of activity:

- Future mobility and autonomous driving in the context of the SHOW project
- Manoeuvre assistance for connected vehicles (PoDIUM focus)
- Workshop discussions on use cases and commercialization of CAV technologies for VRUs and mobility

Description of activity: The workshop explored future mobility concepts, including autonomous driving, and presented PoDIUM's use cases related to connected vehicle manoeuvre assistance. Participants discussed potential next steps for technology commercialization and shared feedback.

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Collection of ideas and opinions on future technologies
- Insights into commercialization opportunities
- Feedback from business partners and municipalities

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: SWARCO Italia

2.3. IN2CCAM / AUGMENTED CCAM – EUCAD 2023

Date/timeline of activity: 03.-04.05.2023

Format of activity: Conference / Breakout session / Exhibition

Topic(s) of activity: CCAM infrastructure, Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI), EU R&I projects, mobility management

Description of activity: PoDIUM participated in the 4th European Conference on Connected and Automated Driving (EUCAD 2023), co-organised by the European Commission, CCAM Partnership, and the FAME project. PoDIUM co-organised Breakout Session 2: "Progressing towards CCAM-hosting and enabling infrastructures", moderated by Vasilis Sourlas (ICCS, PoDIUM coordinator), alongside other EU projects such as IN2CCAM and AUGMENTED CCAM. The session focused on infrastructure requirements for CCAM deployment and the integration of physical and digital infrastructure for traffic and mobility management.

Results/outcomes/achievements: Presented PoDIUM's PDI solutions and infrastructure approach, strengthened collaboration with fellow EU projects, and increased visibility among policymakers, researchers, and industry stakeholders.

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: ICCS

2.4. C-Roads TF Service Harmonisation

Date/timeline of activity: 21.12.2023

Format of activity: PoDIUM Use Cases Presentation in C Roads Service Harmonisation Task Force Telco

Topic(s) of activity:

- PoDIUM overall architecture
- Use cases in German, Spanish and Italian Living Labs
- Discussion, feedback & questions

Description of activity:

PoDIUM engaged with the C-Roads Task Force on Service Harmonisation to present relevant use cases and explore their contribution to the Task Force objectives. Feedback was collected to ensure alignment and applicability.

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Identification of mutual interest and potential for follow-up activities
- Sharing of PoDIUM specifications, including message protocols, with C-Roads TF2/TF3 chairs

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: ATE, ICCS, UULM, AAE, ETRA, LINKS

2.5. ENVELOPE / EVENTS – *Connecting Europe Days 2024*

Date/timeline of activity: 02.-05.04.2024

Format of activity: Conference / Exhibition stand with ENVELOPE & EVENTS projects

Topic(s) of activity: Innovation in transport and mobility, CCAM (Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility), sustainability, EU-funded projects showcase

Description of activity: Connecting Europe Days gathered over 2,500 participants from across Europe and beyond to explore innovation and research in the transport and mobility sectors. PoDIUM, represented by project coordinator ICCS, joined the event with a stand shared with the ENVELOPE and EVENTS projects. Visitors could learn about PoDIUM's vision for accelerating CCAM services in Europe and its five use cases to be demonstrated in Germany, Spain, and Italy.

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Raised visibility of PoDIUM among European transport and mobility stakeholders.
- Promoted project objectives, Living Labs, and use cases.
- Strengthened collaboration with related EU projects (ENVELOPE and EVENTS).
- Launched a new PoDIUM video providing a comprehensive overview of the project.

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: ICCS

2.6. In-Move by Railgroup

Date/timeline of activity: 08.05.2024

Format of activity: Presentation of PODIUM as part of the Workshop: European Projects in Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM)

Topic(s) of activity:

- PoDIUM project objectives and use cases
- Demonstration schedule and project Q&A

Description of activity:

Networking and discussions focused on synergies between PoDIUM and the In-Move cluster, as well as other related CCAM projects.

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Established connections and explored collaboration opportunities with MODI, SPINE, and AUGMENTED CCAM projects

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: ENIDE

2.7. MODI / Augmented CCAM / TANGENT

Date/timeline of activity: 30.05.2024

Format of activity: Online joint workshop with presentations from CCAM projects and industry leaders

Topic(s) of activity: Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI), connectivity, cooperation, CCAM integration in passenger and freight transport

Description of activity:

PoDIUM participated in the online workshop “PDI Connectivity and Cooperation for CCAM Solutions”, organised by IN-MOVE by Railgroup. The event explored how PDI, connectivity, and cooperation underpin the integration of CCAM services in European transport, with applications for both passenger and freight mobility. The agenda featured a keynote on smart infrastructure, presentations on advanced materials for PDI, and a roundtable on New Generation PDI Innovation Projects. At the roundtable, Dr. Lazaros Gkatzikis (ICCS) presented PoDIUM’s work on PDI developments and CCAM ecosystem analysis, alongside contributions from MODI, AUGMENTED CCAM, and TANGENT.

Results/outcomes/achievements: Showcased PoDIUM's role in shaping Europe's CCAM ecosystem, strengthened collaboration with fellow PDI projects, and engaged stakeholders on integration challenges and opportunities.

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: ICCS, TENAL

2.8. AWARD

Date/timeline of activity: 13.06.2024

Format of activity: Poster session as part of the AWARD 2nd Final Conference: Revolutionizing Logistics – A European Conference on Automation in Logistics

Topic(s) of activity: Participation in the Projects Rollup Exhibition

Description of activity:

Networking and discussions about synergies among AWARD and PODIUM, and other CCAM-related projects.

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Identification of collaboration opportunities with MODI, ALICE, and other related initiatives

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: ENIDE

2.9. ROADVIEW / CCAM Partnership / AI-SEE / AWARD / EVENTS / IN2CCAM

Date/timeline of activity: 24.09.2024

Format of activity: Project pitch during cluster event

Topic(s) of activity: CCAM research and innovation, EU project collaboration, barriers and success factors, mobility solutions

Description of activity: PoDIUM joined the CCAM Cluster Event alongside ROADVIEW, the CCAM Partnership, AI-SEE, AWARD, EVENTS, and IN2CCAM. The programme featured project pitches, video demonstrations, and a panel discussion on barriers and success factors for CCAM in Europe. PoDIUM presented its work on Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI), reinforcing its role in advancing CCAM deployment.

Results/outcomes/achievements: Strengthened collaboration with fellow projects, showcased PoDIUM outcomes, and contributed to EU-level discussions on CCAM challenges and opportunities.

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: ICCS

2.10. C-Roads Spain

Date/timeline of activity: 06.11.2024

Format of activity: Meeting as part of PoDIUM Plenary Meeting

Topic(s) of activity: C-ITS deployment, PoDIUM Use Cases Spain and Italy

Description of activity:

Presentation of the PoDIUM Use Cases and schedule for the demonstrations, presentation of C-Roads Spain/SCALE/DS4MOVEUS, project-related Q&A sessions and clarifications.

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Exchange of contact information for organisations involved in C-ITS developments in northern Spain and in the Basque region.
- Insights into Use Cases and demonstration progress, Results and detailed technical outcomes which relate to the PoDIUM demonstration phase
- Agreement to follow up with detailed information exchange at the PoDIUM demonstration events (both PoDIUM demonstration sites in Spain)

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: All partners

Other relevant information: Follow-up with information exchange at the PoDIUM demonstration events in Spain

2.11. SCALE (Spain)

Date/timeline of activity: 06.11.2024

Format of activity: Meeting as part of PoDIUM Plenary Meeting

Topic(s) of activity: C-ITS deployment, PoDIUM Use Cases Spain and Italy

Description of activity:

Presentation of the PoDIUM Use Cases and schedule for the demonstrations, presentation of C-Roads Spain/SCALE/DS4MOVEUS, project-related Q&A sessions and clarifications

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Exchange of contact information for organisations involved in C-ITS developments in northern Spain and in the Basque region.
- Insights into Use Cases and demonstration progress, Results and detailed technical outcomes which relate to the PoDIUM demonstration phase

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: All partners

2.12. MODI / Augmented CCAM / SLICE – Tomorrow Mobility World Congress 2024

Date/timeline of activity: 07.11.2024

Format of activity: CCAM Agora session at Tomorrow Mobility World Congress in Barcelona (guest project participation)

Topic(s) of activity:

- Large-scale CCAM demonstrations
- PDI and digitisation
- Cross-project collaboration
- Energy efficiency in CCAM projects

Description of activity:

- Participation in CCAM Agora discussions with other projects (MODI, ACCAM)
- Dissemination of PoDIUM PDI approach and engagement with European experts

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- CCAM Agora session with other CCAM projects including MODI, and ACCAM with dissemination purposes.
- Engagement in the discussions with MODI, ACCAM and Industry leaders and Academics in PDI/CCAM from all over Europe with focus on Southern Europe.

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: TENAL

2.13. IN-MOVE by Railgroup (Cluster)

Date/timeline of activity: 21.-22.11.2024

Format of activity: Keynote presentation and discussion

Topic(s) of activity:

- PoDIUM project
- Use Cases in German, Spanish and Italian Living Labs
- PDI approach in PoDIUM
- Discussion, feedback and Q&A

Description of activity:

Presentation of PoDIUM from the PDI perspective, highlighting its relevance for digitalisation and sustainability in the railway sector.

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Dissemination of PoDIUM vision
- Exchange of lessons learned in Railway and multi-modal transport
- Engagement with industry leaders and academics in Germany and Spain

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: TENAL

2.14. EVENTS / CONNECT / ConnRAD

Date/timeline of activity: 11.12.2024

Format of activity: Joint workshop on “CCAM Trust Assessment for Safety and Security”

Topic(s) of activity: Trust assessment for safety and security

Description of activity:

Workshop with short presentations and discussions from all participating projects.

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Established a joint understanding of trust from multiple perspectives

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: UULM

2.15. Integrated CCAM Technologies Cluster

Date/timeline of activity: 12.03.2025

Format of activity: Kick-Off Meeting / CCAM Cluster 4 Launch

Topic(s) of activity: Launch of the Integrated CCAM Technologies Cluster, cross-project collaboration, interoperability, CCAM technologies, AI, digital twins, advanced sensing, infrastructure-enabled automation

Description of activity: The Kick-Off Meeting marked the official launch of the Integrated CCAM Technologies Cluster, a strategic alliance of six EU-funded projects — PoDIUM, AITHENA, CONDUCTOR, EVENTS, FRODDO, and iEXODDUS — dedicated to advancing Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) technologies. The meeting introduced the Cluster’s objectives to foster synergies, knowledge exchange, and cross-project collaboration to accelerate innovation, enhance interoperability, and maximize the impact of research efforts in automated and connected mobility.

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Formal launch of the Integrated CCAM Technologies Cluster to coordinate six leading EU CCAM projects.
- Agreement on shared objectives: interoperability, safety and resilience, technology adoption, and standardized methodologies for AI, digital twins, and infrastructure integration.
- Establishment of a shared document folder to facilitate ongoing collaboration and information exchange
- Strengthened connections and synergies between project representatives, setting the foundation for future joint workshops, publications, and events.

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: ICCS, ERTICO

Other relevant information: Joint dissemination activities and participation at demos/final events.

2.16. Workshop on Trustworthy AI

Date/timeline of activity: 25.-26.03.2025

Format of activity: Stakeholder workshop for cross EU activities and research liaison

Topic(s) of activity: Exchange EU action findings and expert views on Trustworthy AI

Description of activity: The workshop aimed at identifying challenges to ensure reliability, transparency, and alignment with fundamental rights of AI systems.

The 2-day workshop included 3 thematic panel, one working session and one discussion session to shape “Roadmap for AI Trustworthiness”. PoDIUM was in one panel session together with AI4CCAM, Aithena and the SUNRISE project.

Results/outcomes/achievements: Prof. Michael Buchholz (UULM) presented PoDIUM challenges in the context of AI Trustworthiness, during a panel on Trustworthiness Assessment of Data in CCAM.

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: UULM

2.17. AUGMENTED CCAM – EUCAD 2025

Date/timeline of activity: 13.-15.05.2025

Format of activity: Conference / Exhibition / Live demonstrations

Topic(s) of activity: Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM), multi-connectivity, trust and integrity, cooperative perception, intersection safety, clustering and synergies

Description of activity: EUCAD 2025, organised by the European Commission with the CCAM Partnership and the FAME project, gathered European and international stakeholders to discuss the deployment of smart and sustainable mobility. The conference featured technical and policy sessions, an exhibition, and live demonstrations, offering EU-funded projects a joint platform to present their results.

PoDIUM shared an exhibition stand with the AUGMENTED CCAM project, where visitors could learn more about the project. Giorgos Zacharopoulos from ICCS, PoDIUM day-to-day coordinator, presented the project’s objectives and achievements, connecting with stakeholders across the CCAM community and exploring future collaborations.

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Technical demonstrations by the German Living Lab, showcasing multi-connectivity solutions for CCAM data transmission, combining 5G and 60 GHz mmWave ad-hoc communication with a software scheduler for enhanced reliability through selective redundancy.
- Technical demonstrations by the Italian Living Lab, presenting use cases on trust and integrity for intersection safety, featuring roadside units, applications, and traffic light infrastructure.

Visitors also explored videos highlighting the Trust Platform Module (TPM) and a Roadside Unit equipped with LiDAR and a camera that generated Cooperative Perception Messages (CPMs) and a Digital Twin of the intersection.

- Vehicle showcase with Stellantis-CRF: In collaboration with the Hi-Drive project, PoDIUM presented the shared Maserati Levante connected and automated vehicle, supporting both projects' use cases.
- Strengthening synergies with other projects: PoDIUM engaged with fellow iCCAM Tech Cluster projects — FRODDO, EVENTS, Althena, CONDUCTOR, and iEXODDUS — to discuss joint activities, explore clustering opportunities, and reinforce collaboration.
- Exhibition booth with AUGMENTED CCAM

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: ICCS, UDE, CRF, LINKS

2.18. FRODDO / AUGMENTED CCAM / IN2CCAM / CONDUCTOR – ITS Europe 2025

Date/timeline of activity: 19.-21.05.2025

Format of activity: Joint Special Interest Session (SIS) / Conference presentation

Topic(s) of activity: Traffic efficiency, emergency response, vulnerable road users (VRUs), Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM), urban traffic management, integrated physical and digital infrastructure

Description of activity: In SIS 24: “Traffic efficiency and safety for VRUs and emergency response”, PoDIUM participated alongside FRODDO, ACCAM, IN2CCAM, and CONDUCTOR, showcasing collaborative solutions from European pilot sites. Organised by PoDIUM and moderated by Vasilis Sourlas (ICCS), the session highlighted PoDIUM’s Spanish Living Lab use case on emergency vehicle prioritisation and VRU safety in Barcelona, demonstrating integration of CCAM technologies into urban infrastructure.

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Showcased PoDIUM’s Living Lab use case for emergency vehicle prioritisation and VRU protection.
- Highlighted collaborative CCAM solutions with FRODDO, ACCAM, IN2CCAM, and CONDUCTOR.
- Demonstrated practical integration of digital and physical infrastructure for safer, more efficient urban traffic.
- Increased visibility among policymakers, researchers, and industry stakeholders

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: ICCS, ETRA I+D

2.19. ESERCOM-D – ITS Europe 2025

Date/timeline of activity: 20.05.2025

Format of activity: Joint session "SIS 61 CCAM impact on vulnerable urban road user safety – opportunities or hopes" at ITS Europe 2025

Topic(s) of activity: PoDIUM project presentation, objectives, use cases, demonstration schedule, project Q&A

Description of activity:

Networking and discussions on synergies among PoDIUM and related CCAM projects (ESERCOM-D, MODI, GAMMS), focusing on safety impacts for cyclists and pedestrians.

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Addressed barriers to CCAM adoption
- Shared lessons from demonstration projects
- Promoted cross-fertilisation among urban leaders, OEMs, and academics

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: ENIDE

2.20. GAMMS

Date/timeline of activity: 11.07.2025

Format of activity: Poster session, Projects Rollup Exhibition

Topic(s) of activity: Networking and discussions on urban mobility, AI, high-accuracy navigation, and autonomous vehicles

Description of activity:

PoDIUM participated in discussions on synergies with GAMMS and other related projects.

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Networking and exploration of collaboration opportunities with GAMMS, ESERCOM-D, MODI, In-Move, etc.

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: ENIDE

2.21. FRODDO – ITS World 2025

Date/timeline of activity: 28.08.2025

Format of activity: Joint Special Interest Session (SIS) / Conference presentation

Topic(s) of activity: Traffic efficiency, CCAM, Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI), international collaboration (Europe, Canada, US)

Description of activity: At the ITS World Congress 2025, PoDIUM contributed to SIS 66: "Traffic Efficiency and Safety Through CCAM: Enhancing Physical and Digital Infrastructure in Europe, Canada, and the US", organised by ICCS/I-SENSE Group and moderated by Angelos Amditis (ICCS, ERTICO). The

session showcased how PDI underpins safer and smarter mobility, bringing together European projects and North American initiatives. Evangelia Latsa (ICCS) presented PoDIUM’s work on “Connected Vehicles, Protected People: Smart Traffic Control in Action”. The session also included perspectives from FRODDO (ERTICO), the Nevada Department of Transportation, AYA Consulting, and Esri Canada, highlighting opportunities for collaboration and knowledge exchange across regions.

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Showcased PoDIUM’s vision for smarter traffic control and safer mobility
- Strengthened collaboration with FRODDO and international partners from Canada and the US.
- Positioned PoDIUM within global CCAM and PDI discussions, reinforcing its role in advancing connected road infrastructure.

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: ICCS

2.22. Cultural Road

Date/timeline of activity: 23.09.2025

Format of activity: Workshop

Topic(s) of activity: Cultural Road project; CCAM societal acceptance; cultural & geographical aspects in automated mobility

Description of activity: Workshop held at ATM offices (Barcelona) in the framework of the EU project *Cultural Road*. The session gathered regional mobility stakeholders to present project progress and collect feedback through a guided discussion.

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Shared early project findings with key stakeholders in Barcelona area
- Collected input on societal acceptance, business models and regulatory/operational gaps in CCAM
- Strengthened cooperation among public authorities, industry and research actors at regional level
- Inputs to be integrated into Cultural Road guidelines and contribute to PoDIUM aims on societal and operational integration

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: TENALACH

2.23. SCALE (Italy)

Date/timeline of activity: 15.10.2025

Format of activity: Workshop as part of the PoDIUM Italian Living Lab Demo in Turin

Topic(s) of activity: C-ITS deployment, SCALE Motorway and Urban pilots, PoDIUM use cases

Description of activity: Presentation of SCALE project highlighting the motorway-related and urban-related use cases; presentation of PoDIUM project and all use cases, project-related Q&A sessions and clarifications

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- Insights into synergies within the activities carried out in the PoDIUM Living Labs and in SCALE Motorway and Urban Pilots: exchange of technical details and developments
- Exchange of useful contact details between both projects' partners.

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: Autostrada del Brennero / all partners participating in the workshop

2.24. C-Roads Italy

Date/timeline of activity: 15.10.2025

Format of activity: Workshop as part of the PoDIUM Italian Living Lab Demo in Turin

Topic(s) of activity: C-ITS deployment, C-Roads Italy, PoDIUM use cases

Description of activity: Overview of the concluded projects C-Roads Italy 2 and C-Roads Italy 3 highlighting the motorway-related and urban-related use cases; presentation of PoDIUM project and all use cases, project-related Q&A sessions and clarifications

Results/outcomes/achievements:

- insights on the PoDIUM side in relevant C-Roads Italy activities/findings
- Exchange of useful contact details between both projects' partners.

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: Autostrada del Brennero / all partners participating in the workshop

2.25. Joint activity at Smart City Expo World Congress

Date/timeline of activity: 4.11.2025

Format of activity: Speakers corner at Barcelona City Council booth at Smart City Expo World Congress (SCEWC) 2025

Topic(s) of activity: Presentation of innovation and technology projects with participation of Barcelona City Council or one of its dependent's bodies.

Description of activity: Presentation of the project and dissemination of the final event on 19th November that will take place in Barcelona.

Results/outcomes/achievements: Interoperability among Traffic Management Centre and Emergencies Centre improving safety and making more efficient the Service.

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: ETRA, BCN, IMI

2.26. FRODDO GA

Date/timeline of activity: 26.11.2025

Format of activity: Presentation as part of project FRODDO GA in Athens

Topic(s) of activity: PoDIUM project Overview

Description of activity: Presentation of PoDIUM project and all use cases, project-related Q&A sessions and clarifications

Results/outcomes/achievements:

Exchange of useful contact details between both projects' partners.

PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity: ERTICO / all partners participating in the General Assembly of FRODDO

3. Conclusions

The Deliverable has provided a comprehensive overview of the liaison activities and international cooperation efforts undertaken within Task 7.3 of the PoDIUM project, aligning with the objectives set forth in WP 7. Through structured engagement with EU and international R&D initiatives, policy makers, and relevant networks, Task 7.3 has supported PoDIUM's goal of facilitating knowledge transfer, fostering synergies, and promoting alignment with key stakeholders in CCAM and 5G.

The key outcomes of Task 7.3 are the establishment of valuable connections with a wide range of projects and the direct contribution to major initiatives such as C-Roads. These engagements have helped PoDIUM to stay aligned with broader CCAM and 5G developments in Europe and integrate insights from external stakeholders, which are essential for overcoming common deployment barriers and supporting the practical adoption of PoDIUM's findings.

Task 7.3 activities have been evaluated against two Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): KPI-62, which targets collaboration with at least ten EU and international R&D initiatives, and KPI-63, which focuses on coordination with at least five C-ROADS actions across the EU. These KPIs have been successfully addressed, as detailed in the activity summaries and the subsequent individual reports. PoDIUM has met the liaison objectives through these actions, showing the project's dedication to playing an active role in the CCAM agenda and encouraging a coordinated approach to research and development in Europe.

The connections established and ongoing coordination efforts have created a foundation for further stakeholder interactions, positioning PoDIUM to contribute meaningfully to the advancement of CCAM and 5G initiatives across Europe.

4. Disclaimer of Warranties

The information and views set out in this deliverable are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the following information.

5. Annex

5.1. Report Template

The template below was used to document the PoDIUM liaison activities.

Liaison and Cooperation Activity Report

This liaison and cooperation activities report is a living document which should be filled out and kept up to date for each liaison and cooperation activity with a defined liaison contact by the partner who is responsible for the liaison activities with this contact. The purpose of this report is to provide the necessary information to the Task 7.3 Leader for reporting to the European Commission and writing D7.10 – Report on liaison and cooperation activities.

There are two table templates in this document:

Table A: Information on the liaison and cooperation partner

Table B: Conducted liaison and cooperation activity – this table is to be filled out **each time a liaison or cooperation activity is conducted** with the liaison contact (for example technical meeting or paper). In case of regular and repetitive activities, please align with ATE on the reporting frequency.

For general guidelines on conducting liaison and cooperation activities, see [the guidelines here](#).

Table A:

Information on liaison and cooperation contact	
If you make updates to the table, cross over the old information and add new information with a date on which the new information was added	
Name of organization, initiative etc.:	Name
Contact Person in organisation, initiative etc. (will not be reported in Deliverable):	Name of contact person
Link to website of organisation, initiative, etc.:	Link
PoDIUM partner conducting liaison and cooperation activities:	Organisation and name of person(s)

Table B:

Conducted liaison and cooperation activity	
Format of activity:	<i>Technical meeting, document review etc.</i>
Timing:	<i>Date of activity, or timing if longer activity</i>
Topic(s) of activity:	<i>Note topic(s) of activity</i>
Description of activity:	<i>Short description of the conducted activity</i>
Results/outcomes/achievements:	<i>Results, achievements and other outcomes which relate to PoDIUM aims outlined in table A or are otherwise important, i.e. description of harmonised agreement on topic X</i>
PoDIUM partner organising/participating in activity:	<i>Organisation and name of person(s)</i>
Link(s) to documentation (if applicable):	<i>PoDIUM internal documentation on Redmine or public documentation online</i>
Other relevant information:	<i>i.e. next steps</i>